

USING DIFFERENT METHODS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract: *In this article, the use of innovative methods in teaching English, explaining the methodology of language material to language learners, and the law that caused positive innovations in education are fully described.*

Key words: *methodology, pedagogical principles, positive updates, innovative methods.*

Introduction:

This sounds like a common sense idea, but it's one that is overlooked by many teachers. You should know that at this age, students are still learning how to hold a pencil, use scissors, or even learn their first language. It can be very rewarding to see young students improve immediately between these ages, but you need to be very patient. So my first piece of advice is that you need to enjoy teaching elementary students. If you have very limited experience or feel uncomfortable, then you may never get used to this environment.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Children try to learn foreign languages from the first grade of general secondary school. Finding the right teaching methodology that produces measurable and effective results is not so easy. In some countries of the world, the most common approach for all levels of education is the traditional method. In traditional classes, the teacher actively works with children, chooses different types of activities: writing, reading, repeating. However, the disadvantage is that due to the large number of students, it is not always correct to check the success rate of the studied material.

After the independence of our country, the desire of young people to learn foreign languages increased, and many conditions for language learning are created by our country.

As our first president Islam Karimov noted: "Currently, teaching foreign languages is of great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. Today, for our country, which is striving to take its rightful place in the world community, in solidarity with our foreign partners, There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our nation, which is building its great future in cooperation."

One of the laws that caused particularly positive updates is the Decision of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" No. PQ-1875. In accordance with this decision, in order to further improve our desire to teach foreign languages, mainly English, from the primary grade, we offer various interesting English lessons from the 1st grade in general schools. teaching in the style of games and at the same time forming the oral speech of students, and starting from the 2nd grade, the transition to teaching the alphabet, reading and grammar using modern, innovative methods began step by step.

Results:

In recent times, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing day by day. Because, in the process of life, living without understanding the English language is becoming more and more difficult. But language learning also depends on age.

Even scientists have proven that children learn languages faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are children's natural tendency to learn a language, their strong ability to imitate, children's time to learn a language more than adults, and their quick memory of learned information.

The following innovative methods can be used to teach English in a meaningful and interesting way:

•Visual recall It is known that young children remember more what they see than what they hear. Therefore, the lesson is taught with the help of various visual aids, posters, something visible and often used in everyday life, teaching new vocabulary by writing on objects, and different sentences with the participation of the new vocabulary learned. make up

For example, writing on a copybook, chair, blackboard, pen, window, etc. Because these items are constantly in sight and used in everyday life, the child learns these words involuntarily.

Discussion:

English language teaching methodology, general (speech orientation, limited and integrated teaching, solving exercises, taking into account language experience), special (teaching English using speech samples, language exercises and speech practice) , interdependence of types of speech activity, development of oral speech, approach to natural speech in a foreign language, further improvement of the elementary stage), special (teaching grammar, teaching vocabulary, teaching reading and the principles of using speech writing in English language teaching) have been developed. We considered a communicative approach to teaching foreign languages in primary education when summarizing pedagogical principles.

Students of the bachelor's level of education are required to learn the methodology of foreign language teaching in schools, to acquire practical knowledge of the methodology of teaching foreign languages to children in the process of independent learning.

1. The requirements for acquiring theoretical knowledge are as follows:

- Complete knowledge of the purpose, tasks, subject, research methods, methodical concepts, tools, methods, principles, methods, exercise system of the foreign language teaching methodology in elementary grades;
- to explain the methodology of language material to language learners;
- effectively know how to teach listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing skills in a foreign language;
- knowing the planning, organization, lesson plan and rating system of the foreign language teaching process.

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